

Editorial

The Stories We Should/Not Tell—or, The Great Traversal

David M. Bowers¹

The Journal

ABSTRACT: This editorial introduces the second volume of the *Journal for Theoretical & Marginal Mathematics Education (JTM-ME)*. This volume marks our second year of active publication. While we (the editors) did not plan for nor solicit it, most of our accepted submissions for this issue are types of stories. Further, they can be seen as “dangerous” stories because they are acts of disclosure. They were all reviewed using our Open Review process. To honor the risk undertaken by the authors represented herein, we theme this volume as containing the stories we should/not tell. The reader is advised to consider the signifier “should/not” as a dialectic: the fact that these stories should not be told—due their dangerousness—is triple-fold the reason for precisely why they should be. In psychoanalysis, testimony can only be given after a phantasy is traversed. The authors in this volume—by telling the stories they shouldn’t—have traversed phantasies through the Open Review process. The result is that what you will read in this volume are testimonies. Taken together, we characterize this second volume of *JTM-ME* as a marker or signal of “The Field’s Great Traversal” which, we hope, will implicate an increasing number of researchers in the coming years.

KEYWORDS: critique of research; academic publishing; traversal; storytelling; narrative; authority

“If you’re silent about your pain, they’ll kill you and say you enjoyed it.”

—Zora Neale Hurston (1937/2006), *Their Eyes Were Watching God*

May We Briefly Provoke You?—or, The Messiness of Truth

You are about to read a collection of stories. As stories, they function as *testimonies*. Testimony itself is mathematical, according to Lacanian Algebra (the mathematical structure of the unconscious; for a specific explanation, see Tupinambá, 2021). For this reason, we suggest that

¹ Associate Editor. Department of Theory & Practice in Teacher Education, University of Tennessee–Knoxville, Knoxville, Tennessee, USA. Email: bowers@cppi.me. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9467-9602>

² Associate Editor. Department of Mathematics, East Stroudsburg University, East Stroudsburg, PA, USA. Email: dubbs@cppi.me. <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6852-7579>

³ Editor-in-Chief. Department of Mathematics, Westfield State University, Westfield, MA, USA. Email: moore@cppi.me. <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5365-0961>

while many of the articles in this issue seem to be extraordinarily “marginal” for our field, we argue that, because of the mathematics of testimony, they are in fact quite central to everyone’s experience of being a researcher or teacher in mathematics education. It is up to you, the reader, to read these contributions with your flesh. We (the editors) do not comment on them at length here. They stand on their own. Rather, Bowers has chosen to add their own exposition (below) to illustrate the aforementioned point about how the rhetorical acts in this volume implicate everyone. It is the analysts (the authors) who have constructed their trust in us (the editors) with these testimonies. But, and here is the crucial point, we (the editors) nor you (the readers) know any better as a result of engaging these articles. We are all still trapped in ignorance. However, these stories are privileged writings, and should be treated as such. We (the editors) *do not know*... and *neither do you*. Therefore, we let these stories *stand* on their own, and *speak*. In these testimonial acts of disclosure, there is found a “truth.”⁴ This “truth” cannot be “known” in the scientific sense; rather, it must be felt in the flesh. We contend that you, the reader, will also “feel them” when you read them. More traditional methodologies for conducting the research to produce these articles would have failed almost immediately. The methodologies employed by the authors herein are instances of how “research” that is “not scientific” can indeed produce profound “knowledge” that is itself excluded from scientific speech. If we (the editors) tried to say what these stories mean (viz. that we “know” what they mean), we would essentially be proving our ignorance in a proof by contradiction.

Whipple (this volume) gives an autoethnographic account of his life in mathematics and sports, and how his (trans)gender has structured and unified these critical aspects of himself. Whipple’s article is punctuated by photographs of his own childhood. We encourage the reader to read this article in relief against the more commonplace gender research of the field.

Ohsiek (this volume) gives an autoethnographic account of a feminine complaint against graduate level mathematics education; in her case, it relates to a Master of Science degree in mathematics. Her exposé takes the form of collages, poems, and songs; the present form of her work was adapted from her Master’s thesis.

Cordero-Siy and Gómez Marchant (this volume) give an account of a counterstory about the experience of a non-White doctoral mathematics education student navigating the White academic machine of the Ph.D. Their account is presented as a playscript, with commentary to guide the reader’s thinking.

Ernest (this volume) provides a new account of necessity and authority in mathematics. While his article is not a “story” per se, we engaged in an innovative pairing of author and reviewer for the Open Review process. Ernest, the preeminent philosopher of mathematics education, has been writing on the topic for decades, and for this article, worked with Dr. Michael Skyer, a scholar of critical disability and deaf education. Thus, Ernest’s article in the present issue is a “story” of sorts—a story of what can happen when unusual pairings of scholars come together to “work out”—from different perspectives—conundrums that affect multiple fields of research.

Finally, Bowers (this volume) provides a critical review of *Landscapes of Investigation*, a new edited volume by Miriam Godoy Penteadó and Ole Skovsmose (2022). In many ways, this text can be seen as the product of the authors’ decades-long work to develop critical mathematics education as a subfield. Their progeny now includes a breadth of researchers, including early career researchers and doctoral students, who have contributed to this volume. It is sure to become a foundational text.

⁴ These comments are based on Moore’s haphazard recollections and reflections on various Lacanian and Heideggerian texts over the years: they are the product of an “overall ruminating” on these theorists’ work, recalled with vagueness on purpose, as evoked irregularly by his work on producing of the contents of this issue.

A Testimony by Bowers—or, The Chaos of Silence

In a more hegemonically aligned research outlet, one of the strongest loci of power discrepancy lays between Editor(s) and Author(s), with the former able to wield substantially more institutional power. One place this power might generally but invisibly be felt lies in terms of who readers are “entitled to know,” in direct analogy to a similar power discrepancy commonly felt between teachers and students (see, for example, Grace A. Chen’s forthcoming book chapter “Choosing Cruel Optimism: What Relational Ethics Offers “Equitable” Mathematics Education”). At this Journal we are dissatisfied with reifying that power discrepancy—it would be ethically fraught to publish such incisively vulnerable pieces as those that have been contributed to this issue without extending at least some modicum of the same vulnerability. Of course, just as our contributing Authors shared vulnerability towards their own didactic purposes concomitant with their ethical purposes, so too do we. David, resident Anarchist, shares below a sketch of their experience of Autistic situational mutism, focusing on how the experience sometimes felt as an Elementary student. Below, we expand on how that autoethnographic excerpt can be used (and felt/experienced) as an embodied analogy of some of the patterns that emerge in the research publication industry.

The classroom was filled with hustle and bustle, that creative chaos that joyously permeates so many of the best classrooms. Even in retrospect, I love that teacher. They cared for all of us deeply, even when they did not always know how to care for us. That latter issue, though, is far from superficial. So many times I remember them soliciting student voice, but never in a way that actually allowed me to speak. Situational mutism cares not for my desire to speak, cares not for the fact that I do in fact have the words—I have no way to voice them, or am unable to voice them in forms that are meaningful to me. Situational mutism cares not for the teacher’s desire to hear my words, to gain whatever insight they may into my inner world—the words are pinned beneath the weight of sociomaterial hegemony and have no way out, and were I to bend them to fit the space the external world allowed me they would break, become a different message entirely. The words are stuck here with me, trapped and claustrophobic, unable to transition from internal thought to external action, leaving me trapped in my own silence amidst the ceaseless noise of the world around me. My will is drowned out against cultural momentum that disavows my humanity, and my screams go unheard, echoing across my thoughts and memories but unable to materialize, invisible within the ontological experiences of everyone else in the room. Internally I scream and thrash and fight, but like the moments before you waken from the nightmare my body was still and my voice silent, and in that silence the story becomes one of compliance and acquiescence. I sat alone in the storm that wracked my nervous system, lightning crackling across my skull, and I was told I enjoyed it.

I must emphasize, too, that this was a best-case scenario. Other teachers actively desired against hearing the thoughts of myself and my classmates. Yet even with a teacher who sincerely desired to make space for my marginalized (disabled, queer) being, they were limited in proportion with the extent to which they yet reified the status quo. Even a teacher who sincerely valued my humanity nonetheless created a classroom that kept me silent and nondisruptive, a classroom that continued to treat status quo violences as inviolable reality. This kept those teachers professionally safe in many respects, but did so by constructing children like me as acceptable casualties. As a teenager thence young adult reflecting on these experiences, I was eventually led to an inescapable conclusion... One can not count on those in power, even those who love you, to make space for your voice. Sooner or later, we must make this space for ourselves, defying those in power to stop us.

Dare We Traverse It?—or, Some Tiring Recapitulations

The above is an autoethnographic reflection shared by David, but like all autoethnography it is not just about them—it is a story of society, of ideology that nests so deeply in our assumptions and practices that it becomes nigh inescapable. Like the teacher in the story, so many mathematics education Journals and other publication outlets are fundamentally attached to status quo assumptions about the aesthetics, routines, and practices of our field that they leave scant space for truly marginalized (read: disruptive) voice. White (cis-hetero Patriarchal, Abled, etc.) Capitalist logics trap us (Miarka et al., 2023), even in “equity oriented” spaces (Bullock, 2023). Over and over again, even when marginalized voices are actively solicited instead of being told they demand too much or that they take up too much space, we are instead offered space only on the condition that we give up enough of ourselves and our message to make it “acceptable” in the eyes of those in power. Over and over again, we are rendered mute by the situations and systems those in power uphold. Over and over again, it is left to marginalized people to create spaces for themselves, as even the most loving of those in power neglect to truly make space for us. We have seen this with the founding of Mathematics Education and Society, the Colloquium of Research in Critical Mathematics Education, the Journal of Urban Mathematics Education, TODOS, and so much more, and we are seeing it again with this Journal. Reading the articles in this issue, so many involve the telling of stories that previously had scant opportunity to find a home in the mathematics education publishing landscape. Marginalized people have been calling for space to share these stories for as long as we have been around (i.e. since the beginning), but as always it was left to us, even as scholars with little to no institutional power, to create this space. It is with solidarity and pride that we now share these stories with our community writ broad.

As David loved their teacher, so too do we love those who organize and run the very Journals we are pushing back against. Contrary to colonial logics that would dictate “either/or” thinking, the love and angst this leaves us with are not two separate objects but instead one larger experience. The emancipatory potential of our field’s dominant publication outlets is, as ever, constrained in proportion to the extent to which these institutions are willing to eschew Colonial logics in their institutional substance, but it is not easy to grow beyond Colonial/White ideology. Even a brief perusal of the tenets of White Supremacy Culture (Brown et al, 2016) should give us pause when reflecting on many taken-for-granted aspects of publication within and beyond our field: Objectivity, Paternalism, perfectionism, either/or thinking, fear of open conflict, individualism, right to comfort, and so forth. These collectively impose a steep barrier on what sorts of voice publication outlets are making space for. We love those who run these major institutions of mathematics education, but are simultaneously left sitting with the angst of reality. Predatory journals have been defined as “[...] entities that prioritize self-interest at the expense of scholarship,” (Grudniewicz et al., 2019, 210) and it is worth sitting with the question of to what extent are our dominant Journals made predatory by virtue of enacting a predatory (White, Capitalist) ideology. Connecting to White Supremacy Culture, either/or thinking coupled with right to comfort makes it relatively easy to shrug off this predatory nature by virtue of adding additional stipulations which our most respected institutions might not meet, e.g. adding that predatory journals “are characterized by false or misleading information, deviation from best [i.e. normalized] editorial and publication practices, a lack of transparency, and/or the use of aggressive and indiscriminate solicitation practices.” (Grudniewicz et al., 2019, 210) However, in terms of the pursuit of both material capital (mostly held by publication companies) and cultural capital (mostly held by Editors and, to a lesser extent, reviewers), there may be additional discomfort to navigate in truly holding our institutions accountable for the pursuit of self-interest over collective liberation.

In solidarity, we (the collective comprising CPPI-ME and JTM-ME) look forward to hearing so many more (of your) stories in the coming years.

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